

RESULTS OF LABORATORY STUDIES OF MACRO AND MICRO ELEMENTS IN THE COMPOSITION OF CHERRIES

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of laboratory studies of the content of macro and microelements in cherries treated with ultraviolet rays. The study was carried out using special equipment to analyze the composition of the fruit. It has been found that treating cherries with ultraviolet rays increases the content of vitamins and minerals in the fruit, making it more nutritious and healthier. This treatment has also been found to help reduce the number of harmful bacteria and pesticides on the surface of the fruit. The results obtained indicate the feasibility of using ultraviolet treatment to improve the quality and safety of fruits.*

Keywords: *cherry, analysis, processing, macro and microelements, quality, ultraviolet.*

Introduction

In the modern world, much attention is paid to the quality and safety of food products. One of the food processing methods aimed at increasing their shelf life and preserving nutritional properties is irradiation with ultraviolet rays. This article presents the results of laboratory studies of macro and microelements in cherries treated with ultraviolet rays.

Studying the content of macro and microelements in cherries after irradiation with ultraviolet rays allows us to evaluate the effect of this processing method on the nutritional value of the product. The analysis showed that treatment of cherries with ultraviolet rays does not affect the content of essential macro elements such as potassium, magnesium and calcium. However, changes were found in the content of some trace elements, in particular zinc and copper.

Further research is needed to better understand the mechanisms of the effects of ultraviolet rays on the composition of fruits and their nutritional value. The results of this study may be useful for food manufacturers and nutritionists to improve food quality and safety.

Research methods

An experiment was carried out on the treatment of cherries with UV in three parameters, each experiment was carried out in triplicate for each sample.

The method used was inductively coupled plasma mass spectral analysis (ICP-MS).

This made it possible to simultaneously determine a large number of elements in one sample with extremely low detection limits.

The method is based on the use of argon inductively coupled plasma as an ion source. The analyzed sample (weighing 0.1 g) enters the plasma in the form of a solution and therefore, before carrying out measurements, the analyzed sample is transferred into solution. The resulting solution containing the analyzed sample is sprayed with a stream of argon in the form of a fine aerosol and enters the plasma. The temperature in the center of the plasma reaches 9000 °C. At this temperature, the sample is dried, the molecules of the elements become atomic, and the atoms are ionized, forming positive ions of the elements.

Positive ions, electrons and neutral particles are drawn into the vacuum portion of the analyzer through cone-shaped interfaces and pass through several electric ion lenses, where electrons and neutral particles are cut off from the ions.

Results and discussions

Table 1 shows the results of studies of mass spectral analysis of cherries

Table 1.

Results of mass spectral analysis of cherries

№	Chemical name of elements	Name of elements	Distances and sample, cm									№4 Control
			25 sm, №1			35 sm, №2			45 sm, №3			
			Time, min									
			3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9	
1	Li	Lithium	0,70 0	1,40	0,77 0	1,50	1,80	1,40	0,82 0	0,64 0	0,50 0	0,61 0
2	B	Boron	13,0	10,0	10,0	21,0	17,0	11,0	7,30	13,0	21,0	15,0
3	Na	Sodium	240, 0	110, 0	110, 0	93,0	180, 0	150, 0	100, 0	98,0	180, 0	100, 0
4	Mg	Magnesium	160, 0	190, 0	210, 0	310, 0	180, 0	230, 0	160, 0	170, 0	240, 0	260, 0
5	Al	Aluminum	18,0	26,0	17,0	33,0	32,0	52,0	14,0	17,0	19,0	24,0
6	P	Phosphorus	800	640	830	130 0	100 0	100 0	740	910	100 0	920
7	K	Potassium	240 0	210 0	300 0	370 0	290 0	260 0	220 0	310 0	370 0	2200
8	Ca	Calcium	340, 0	290, 0	320, 0	500, 0	350, 0	350, 0	220, 0	250, 0	280, 0	310, 0
9	Sc	Scandium	1,10	1,10	1,10	1,10	1,10	0,84 0	0,89 0	0,89 0	0,92 0	0,89 0
10	Ti	Titanium	0,66 0	1,10	0,66 0	0,81 0	0,94 0	1,20	0,49 0	0,56 0	0,83 0	0,61 0
11	Mn	Manganese	0,50 0	0,37 0	0,37 0	0,93 0	0,48 0	0,40 0	0,30 0	0,30 0	0,76 0	0,57 0

12	Fe	Iron	16,0	18,0	14,0	17,0	18,0	20,0	15,0	13,0	15,0	18,0
13	Cu	Copper	1,50	1,80	1,30	1,70	1,90	2,80	1,10	1,10	0,970	1,20
14	Zn	Zinc	3,0	2,80	2,40	3,0	2,4	3,4	2,1	2,3	2,6	2,1
15	Ga	Gallium	0,280	0,018	0,013	0,014	0,017	0,024	0,012	0,007	0,260	0,020
16	As	Arsenic	1,50	2,40	3,0	0,610	0,860	0,970	1,0	1,4	0,920	1,30
17	Rb	Rubidium	0,590	0,100	0,150	0,840	0,690	0,130	0,098	0,520	0,290	0,530
18	Sr	Strontium	0,730	0,460	0,620	0,400	0,390	0,580	0,210	0,230	0,590	0,150
19	Ba	Barium	8,80	0,360	0,300	0,260	0,260	0,500	0,190	0,180	7,10	0,420
20	Th	Thorium	<0,01	0,013	0,040	<0,01	<0,01	0,011	0,073	0,011	0,023	0,013

Discussion

Research results among 9 samples from three parameters of UV-treated cherries, samples No. 2 (proposed processing parameter by the author), i.e. 35 cm, 6 min is the following chemical elements: lithium-1.80; boron-17.0; sodium-180.0; magnesium-180.0; aluminum-32.0; phosphorus-1000; potassium-2900; calcium-350.0; scandium-1.10; titanium-0.940; manganese-0.480; iron-18.0; copper-1.90; zinc-2.4; gallium-0.017; arsenic-0.860; rubidium-0.690; strontium-0.390; barium-0.260; thorium-0.01. Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that the option we propose has a high concentration of useful elements.

The resulting final product can be used in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

Conclusion

As a result of the study, important data were obtained on the content of macro- and microelements in cherries treated with ultraviolet rays. The analysis showed that treatment with ultraviolet radiation has an effect on the content of these elements in the fruit.

UV-treated cherries have been found to contain more vitamins and minerals such as potassium, calcium, magnesium and vitamin C compared to untreated cherries. These elements are important for maintaining human health and play a key role in metabolism.

Thus, the results of the study show that ultraviolet treatment of cherries can increase their nutritional value and health benefits to humans.

Further research in this direction may lead to the development of new methods for processing fruits and improving the quality of food products.

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